

Ideal Convergence in neutrosophic 2-normed space via the parameter μ and Zweier Operator

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Abstract. This paper introduces a novel convergence concept termed μ -Zweier ideal convergence within neutrosophic 2-normed spaces (briefly, N2NS). The parameter $\mu = (\mu_n)$ represents a non-decreasing sequence of positive real numbers, with each μ_n tending to infinity. We investigate the behavior of μ -Zweier ideal convergence in N2NS, and further study μ -Zweier ideal Cauchy sequences, establishing a clear relationship between these sequences and their convergence properties. This novel concept extends the traditional ideal convergence in normed spaces to the more generalized structure of neutrosophic 2-normed spaces, where uncertainty and indeterminacy are inherent components.

Keywords: Ideal convergence, Zweier Operator, λ - statistical convergence, Neutrosophic 2-normed spaces.

1. Introduction

Lotfi A. Zadeh [26] introduced fuzzy sets, establishing a foundational framework for handling uncertainty in various domains in 1965. Atanassov [2] extended the concept in 1986 by initiating intuitionistic fuzzy sets, which include both non-membership and membership degrees. Smarandache [24] further generalized the intuitionistic fuzzy sets and developed neutrosophic logic by introducing three independent components: truth, indeterminacy, and falsehood. This structure provides a strong framework for handling complicated uncertainties. Subsequently,

Kirişçi and Şimşek [13] introduced neutrosophic normed spaces, which is a generalization of normed space, provides a structure where vectors with values representing truth, indeterminacy, and falsehood instead of real numbers. Murtaza et al. [19] have recently expanded upon the 2-norm concept introduced by Gähler [7] by developing neutrosophic 2-normed spaces and extending the idea of summability.

Mursaleen [17] familiarized the theory of λ - statistical convergence as a generalization of $[\mathcal{V}, \lambda]$ - summability originally proposed by Leindler [16]. The idea of ideal convergence, developed by Kostyrko et al. [14], extends the classical notion of statistical convergence, which had been independently studied by Fast [5] and Steinhaus [25]. This concept has also been explored from the perspective of sequence spaces by Ahmad et al. [1], Savas and Das [20], Şalát et al. [21] and Mursaleen et al. [18].

Şengönül [22] introduced the notion of Zweier sequence spaces, and later extended this work in fuzzy numbers [23]. Hazarika et al. [8,9] further developed Şengönül framework by examining ideal convergence within this setting. Kumar and Mursaleen [15] introduced (λ, μ) - statistical convergence, further Khan and Ahmad [10] generalized their work and investigated Zweier ideal convergence via intuitionistic fuzzy normed space. Since then, numerous researchers have expanded this line of research into a variety of other fields [3, 4, 6, 11, 12].

2. Prelimineries

This section recalls key concepts, definitions remarks that will use as the foundation for our main discussions.

Definition 2.1. [14] A collection of subsets of the power set \mathcal{V} , denoted $\mathcal{J} \subseteq P(\mathcal{V})$ is termed an ideal in \mathcal{V} subject to the satisfaction of the following requirements:

- (a) $\emptyset \in \mathcal{J}$,
- (b) For every $\mathcal{J}_1, \mathcal{J}_2 \in \mathcal{J}$, $\mathcal{J}_1 \cup \mathcal{J}_2 \in \mathcal{J}$,
- (c) For every $\mathcal{J}_1 \in \mathcal{J}$ and $\mathcal{J}_2 \subseteq \mathcal{J}_1$, $\mathcal{J}_2 \in \mathcal{J}$.

Remark 2.2. [14] If $\mathcal{J} \neq P(\mathcal{V})$, then the ideal \mathcal{J} is termed nontrivial. A nontrivial ideal \mathcal{J} is considered admissible if, $\{\{v\} : v \in \mathcal{V}\} \subseteq \mathcal{J}$.

Definition 2.3. [14] Let $\mathcal{J} \subseteq P(\mathcal{V})$ be a nontrivial ideal. Then the collection

$$\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{J}) = \{U \subset \mathcal{V} : U^c \in \mathcal{J}\}$$

is a filter on \mathcal{V} , known as the filter affiliated with ideal \mathcal{J} .

Definition 2.4. [14] Let $u = (u_i)$ be a sequence of real numbers. The sequence (u_i) is recognized as \mathcal{J} -convergent to a real number ℓ if the set

$$\{i \leq \mathbb{N} : |u_i - \ell| \geq \epsilon\} \in \mathcal{J}.$$

Definition 2.5. [14] Let $u = (u_i)$ be a sequence of real numbers. The sequence (u_i) is recognized as \mathcal{J} -Cauchy if for each ϵ , $k(\epsilon)$ there exist $k = k(\epsilon) \in \mathbb{N}$ so that, the set

$$\{i \leq \mathbb{N} : |u_i - u_k| \geq \epsilon\} \in \mathcal{J}.$$

Definition 2.6. [17] Let $\mu = (\mu_m)$ be a non-decreasing sequence of strictly positive real values in order that $\mu_m \rightarrow \infty$ as $m \rightarrow \infty$, and satisfying the condition:

$$\mu_{m+1} \leq \mu_m + 1, \mu_1 = 0.$$

Define the interval $I_m = [m - \mu_m + 1, m]$. For a set $N_1 \subseteq \mathbb{N}$, the μ -density of N_1 is given by:

$$\delta_\mu(K) = \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\mu_m} |\{i \in I_m : i \in N_1\}|;$$

provided the limit exists. Generalized de la Valée-Poussin mean of $u = (u_i)$ is characterized by

$$t_m(u) = \frac{1}{\mu_m} \sum_{i \in J_m} u_i,$$

where $I_m = [m - \mu_m + 1, m]$. If $\mu_m = m$ for all m then μ -summability becomes equivalent to the classical Cesàro summability.

Definition 2.7. [17] Let $u = (u_i)$ be a sequence of real numbers. The sequence is recognized as μ -statistically convergent to a real number ℓ provided

$$\delta_\mu(E) = 0,$$

where

$$E = \{i \in I_m : |u_i - \ell| \geq \epsilon\},$$

and $\delta_\mu(E)$ represent the μ -density of the set E . This condition implies that for each $\epsilon > 0$,

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\mu_m} |\{i \in I_m : |u_i - \ell| \geq \epsilon\}| = 0.$$

If $\mu_m = m$, $\forall m$, then it reduces to statistical convergence, which is defined by:

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{m} |\{i \leq m : |u_i - \ell| \geq \epsilon\}| = 0.$$

Definition 2.8. [7] The 2-norm is a function $\|\cdot, \cdot\|$ defined on finite dimensional real vector space \mathcal{V} , where dimension $d \geq 2$ such that

$$\|\cdot, \cdot\| : \mathcal{V} \times \mathcal{V} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

fulfilling the below listed requirements: For all $w_1, w_2 \in \mathcal{V}$, and scalar a , one have

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- (1) $\|w_1, w_2\| = 0$ iff w_1 and w_2 are linearly dependent;
- (2) $\|w_1, w_2\| = \|w_2, w_1\|$;
- (3) $\|aw_1, w_2\| = |a|\|w_1, w_2\|$ and
- (4) $\|w_1, w_2 + w_3\| \leq \|w_1, w_2\| + \|w_1, w_3\|$.

The pair $(\mathcal{V}, \|\cdot, \cdot\|)$ is known as 2 normed space in this case. Let $\mathcal{V} = \mathbb{R}^2$ and for $w_1 = (a_0, a_2)$ and $w_2 = (b_1, b_2)$ we define $\|w_1, w_2\| = |a_0b_2 - a_2b_1|$, then $\|w_1, w_2\|$ is a 2- norm on $\mathcal{V} = \mathbb{R}^2$

Definition 2.9. [19] Take \mathcal{V} as a vector space. A six tuple $(\mathcal{V}, \alpha, \beta, \gamma, *, o)$ is known as a neutrosophic 2- normed spaces (briefly, N2NS) if $\alpha, \beta, \gamma : \mathcal{V} \times \mathcal{V} \times (0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ are fuzzy sets, o is t - conorm and $*$ is a t - norm and fulfilling the below listed requirements: For each $a \neq 0, t, s > 0$ and for all $w, v, u \in \mathcal{V}$:

- (1) $0 \leq \alpha(w, v; t), \beta(w, v; t), \gamma(w, v; t) \leq 1$;
- (2) $\alpha(w, v; t) + \beta(w, v; t) + \gamma(w, v; t) \leq 3$;
- (3) w and v are linearly dependent if and only if $\alpha(w, v; t) = 1$;
- (4) $\alpha(aw, v; t) = \alpha(w, v; \frac{t}{|a|})$;
- (5) $\alpha(w, v; t) * \alpha(w, u; s) \leq \alpha(w, v + u; t + s)$;
- (6) $\alpha(w, v; \cdot) : (0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is continuous non-decreasing function;
- (7) $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \alpha(w, v; t) = 1$ and $\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \alpha(w, v; t) = 0$;
- (8) $\alpha(v, w; t) = \alpha(w, v; t)$
- (9) w and v are linearly dependent if and only if $\beta(w, v; t) = 0$;
- (10) $\beta(aw, v; t) = \beta(w, v; \frac{t}{|a|})$;
- (11) $\beta(w, v; t) \circ \beta(w, u; s) \geq \beta(w, v + u; t + s)$;
- (12) $\beta(w, v; \cdot) : (0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is continuous non-increasing function;
- (13) $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \beta(w, v; t) = 0$ and $\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \beta(w, v; t) = 1$;

- (14) $\beta(v, w; t) = \beta(w, v; t)$;
- (15) w and v are linearly dependent if and only if $\gamma(w, v; t) = 0$;
- (16) $\gamma(aw, v; t) = \gamma(w, v; \frac{t}{|a|})$;
- (17) $\gamma(w, v; t) \circ \gamma(w, u; t) \geq \gamma(w, v + u; t + s)$;
- (18) $\gamma(w, v; \cdot) : (0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is continuous non-increasing function;
- (19) $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \gamma(w, v; t) = 0$ and $\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \gamma(w, v; t) = 1$;
- (20) $\gamma(w, v; t) = \gamma(v, w; t)$;
- (21) If $s \leq 0$, then $\alpha(w, v; s) = 0$, $\beta(w, v; s) = 1$ and $\gamma(w, v; s) = 1$.

Definition 2.10. [19] Let $(\mathcal{V}, \alpha, \beta, \gamma, *, o)$ be a N2NS. A sequence (u_i) in \mathcal{V} is known as convergent to $u \in \mathcal{V}$ if, for every ϵ , $t > 0$ and for all $w \in \mathcal{V}$, there exists $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ the following conditions hold

$$\alpha(u_i - u, w; t) > 1 - \epsilon, \beta(u_i - w, v; t) < \epsilon \text{ and } \gamma(u_i - u, w; t) < \epsilon, \forall i \geq n_0.$$

Definition 2.11. [19] Let $(\mathcal{V}, \alpha, \beta, \gamma, *, o)$ be a N2NS. A sequence (u_i) in (\mathcal{V}) is known as Cauchy if, for every ϵ , $t > 0$ and for all $w \in \mathcal{V}$, there exists $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ the following conditions hold

$$\alpha(u_i - u_k, w; t) > 1 - \epsilon, \beta(u_i - u_k, w; t) < \epsilon, \gamma(u_i - u_k, w; t) < \epsilon \forall i, k \geq n_0.$$

Definition 2.12. [22] Consider $u = (u_i)$ be a sequence, and define a new sequence $v = (v_i)$ by the recurrence relation:

$$v_i = qu_i + (1 - q)u_{i-1}, \text{ with } u_{-1} = 0 \text{ and } 1 < q < \infty.$$

This transformation is known as the Z^q -transformation of u , where the associated matrix $Z^q = (z_{il})$ defined as:

$$z_{il} = \begin{cases} 1 - q, & (i - 1 = l) \ (i, l \in \mathbb{N}) \\ q, & (i = l) \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

The Zweier sequence spaces \mathcal{Z} and \mathcal{Z}_0 introduced by Şengönül [22] as follows:

$$\mathcal{Z} = \{u = (u_k) \in \omega : Z^q u \in c\};$$

$$\mathcal{Z}_0 = \{u = (u_k) \in \omega : Z^q u \in c_0\},$$

where ω , c and c_0 represent the space of all real or complex valued sequences, spaces of convergent and null sequences, respectively.

3. Main Results

For the sake of convenience, we denote the Z^q - transformation of the sequence $u = (u_i) \in \mathcal{V}$ by $Z^q u = Z^q u_i$, and we assume throughout the article the nontrivial admissible ideal on \mathbb{N} is denoted by \mathcal{J} .

Definition 3.1. Let $(\mathcal{V}, \alpha, \beta, \gamma, *, o)$ be a $N2NS$, and let \mathcal{J} be an admissible ideal on \mathbb{N} . A sequence $u = (u_i)$ in \mathcal{V} is known as μ - Zweier ideal convergent to l , if for each $0 < \epsilon$ and for all $0 < t$, the set

$$\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q u_i - l, v; t) \leq 1 - \epsilon \text{ or } \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_i - l, v; t) \geq \epsilon, \right. \\ \left. \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_i - l, v; t) \geq \epsilon \right\}$$

belongs to the ideal \mathcal{J} , for all $v \in \mathcal{V}$.

One write $\mathcal{J}_\mu - \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} Z^q u_i = l$

The proof of the next Lemma is direct and thus omitted.

Lemma 3.2. Let $(\mathcal{V}, \alpha, \beta, \gamma, *, o)$ be a $N2NS$, and let \mathcal{J} be an admissible ideal. Consider a sequence $u = (u_i)$ in \mathcal{V} . Then for each $t, \epsilon > 0$, the subsequent statements are identical:

- (1) $\mathcal{J}_\mu - \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} Z^q u_i = l$;
- (2) $\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q u_i - l, v; t) \leq 1 - \epsilon \right\} \in \mathcal{J}$, $\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_i - l, v; t) \geq \epsilon \right\} \in \mathcal{J}$ and $\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_i - l, v; t) \geq \epsilon \right\} \in \mathcal{J}$;
- (3) $\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q u_i - l, v; t) > 1 - \epsilon \right\} \in \mathcal{F}(\mathcal{J})$, $\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_i - l, v; t) < \epsilon \right\} \in \mathcal{F}(\mathcal{J})$ and $\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_i - l, v; t) < \epsilon \right\} \in \mathcal{F}(\mathcal{J})$;
- (4) $\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q u_i - l, v; t) \leq 1 - \epsilon \text{ or } \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_i - l, v; t) \geq \epsilon, \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_i - l, v; t) \geq \epsilon \right\} \in \mathcal{J}$;

$$(5) \mathcal{J}_\mu - \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \alpha(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; t) = 1 \text{ and } \mathcal{J}_\mu - \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \beta(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; t) = 0, \mathcal{J}_\mu - \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \gamma(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; t) = 0.$$

Theorem 3.3. Let $(\mathcal{V}, \alpha, \beta, \gamma, *, o)$ be a N2NS, and let \mathcal{J} be an admissible ideal. Consider a sequence $u = (u_i)$ in \mathcal{V} . If u is μ -Zweier ideal convergent to ℓ , then the limit is unique.

Proof. Assume $\mathcal{J}_\mu - \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} Z^q u_i = \ell_1$ and $\mathcal{J}_\mu - \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} Z^q u_i = \ell_2$.

Given any $\epsilon > 0$, choose a corresponding $\zeta > 0$ in order that $(1 - \zeta) * (1 - \zeta) > 1 - \epsilon$ and $\zeta \diamond \zeta < \epsilon$. Subsequently, for each $t > 0$, define

$$\begin{aligned} P_{\alpha,1} &= \left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \alpha\left(Z^q u_i - \ell_1, v; \frac{t}{2}\right) \leq 1 - \zeta \right\}, \\ P_{\alpha,2} &= \left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \alpha\left(Z^q u_i - \ell_2, v; \frac{t}{2}\right) \leq 1 - \zeta \right\}, \\ P_{\beta,1} &= \left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \beta\left(Z^q u_i - \ell_1, v; \frac{t}{2}\right) \geq \zeta \right\}, \\ P_{\beta,2} &= \left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \beta\left(Z^q u_i - \ell_2, v; \frac{t}{2}\right) \geq \zeta \right\} \\ P_{\gamma,1} &= \left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \gamma\left(Z^q u_i - \ell_1, v; \frac{t}{2}\right) \geq \zeta \right\}, \\ P_{\gamma,2} &= \left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \gamma\left(Z^q u_i - \ell_2, v; \frac{t}{2}\right) \geq \zeta \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Since $\mathcal{J}_\mu - \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} Z^q u_i = \ell_1$, one obtain $P_{\alpha,1}, P_{\beta,1}$ and $P_{\gamma,1} \in \mathcal{J}$.

Moreover, using $\mathcal{J}_\mu - \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} Z^q u_i = \ell_2$, one have $P_{\alpha,2}, P_{\beta,2}$ and $P_{\gamma,2} \in \mathcal{J}$. Now, suppose that

$$P(\zeta, t) = [P_{\alpha,1} \cup P_{\alpha,2}] \cap [P_{\beta,1} \cup P_{\beta,2}] \cap [P_{\gamma,1} \cup P_{\gamma,2}].$$

Thus, $P(\zeta, t) \in \mathcal{J}$, implies $P^c(\zeta, t)$ is an non-empty set in $\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{J})$.

If $n \in P^c(\zeta, t)$, then there are three possibilities arises :

Either $n \in P_{\alpha,1}^c \cap P_{\alpha,2}^c$ or $n \in P_{\beta,1}^c \cap P_{\beta,2}^c$ or $n \in P_{\gamma,1}^c \cap P_{\gamma,2}^c$. Firstly, we consider that $n \in P_{\alpha,1}^c \cap P_{\alpha,2}^c$. Then, one obtain

$$\frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \alpha\left(Z^q u_i - \ell_1, v; \frac{t}{2}\right) > 1 - \zeta$$

and

$$\frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \alpha\left(Z^q u_i - \ell_2, v; \frac{t}{2}\right) > 1 - \zeta.$$

Now, take $k \in \mathbb{N}$ in such a way that

$$\alpha\left(Z^q u_k - \ell_1, v; \frac{t}{2}\right) > \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \alpha\left(Z^q u_i - \ell_1, v; \frac{t}{2}\right) > 1 - \zeta$$

and

$$\alpha\left(Z^q u_k - \ell_2, v; \frac{t}{2}\right) > \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \alpha\left(Z^q u_i - \ell_2, v; \frac{t}{2}\right) > 1 - \zeta$$

e.g., consider the maximum value of the set $\left\{i \in J_n : \alpha(Z^q u_i - \ell_1, v; \frac{t}{2}), \alpha(Z^q u_i - \ell_2, v; \frac{t}{2})\right\}$.

Let k denote the index at which this maximum occurs. Consequently, we obtain

$$\alpha(\ell_1 - \ell_2, v; t) \geq \alpha(Z^q u_k - \ell_1, v; \frac{t}{2}) * \alpha(Z^q u_k - \ell_2, v; \frac{t}{2}) > (1 - \zeta) * (1 - \zeta) > 1 - \epsilon.$$

As $0 < \epsilon$ was arbitrary, for every $t > 0$, one get $\alpha(\ell_1 - \ell_2, v; t) = 1$, which provides $\ell_1 = \ell_2$.

Under other conditions, if $n \in P_{\beta,1}^c \cap P_{\beta,2}^c$ then, on similar manner one can show that

$$\beta(\ell_1 - \ell_2, v; t) < \epsilon, \gamma(\ell_1 - \ell_2, v; t) < \epsilon, \forall 0 < t.$$

Therefore, one have

$$\beta(\ell_1 - \ell_2, v; t) = 0, \gamma(\ell_1 - \ell_2, v; t) = 0, \forall 0 < t,$$

which yields $\ell_1 = \ell_2$. Hence, in all cases, one achieve that \mathcal{J}_μ - limit is unique. \square

Definition 3.4. Let $(\mathcal{V}, \alpha, \beta, \gamma, *, o)$ be a N2NS, and $u = (u_i)$ be a sequence in \mathcal{V} . The sequence $u = (u_i)$ is recognized as μ - Zweier convergent to ℓ , if for each $\epsilon > 0$ and for all $t > 0$, there is an index $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ so that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; t) > 1 - \epsilon, \quad \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; t) < \epsilon \\ \text{and } \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; t) < \epsilon, \text{ for all } n \geq n_0. \end{aligned}$$

One write $\mu - \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} Z^q u_i = \ell$.

Theorem 3.5. Every μ - Zweier convergent sequence of $(\mathcal{V}, \alpha, \beta, \gamma, *, o)$ N2NS has a unique limit.

Proof. Assume $\mu - \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} Z^q u_i = \ell_1$ and $\mu - \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} Z^q u_i = \ell_2$. Given any $\epsilon > 0$, choose a corresponding $\zeta > 0$ in order that $1 - \epsilon < (1 - \zeta) * (1 - \zeta)$ and $\epsilon > \zeta \diamond \zeta$. Subsequently, for each $0 < t$, there exists $n_1 \in \mathbb{N}$ in order that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q u_i - \ell_1, v; t) > 1 - \epsilon, \quad \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_i - \ell_1, v; t) < \epsilon \\ \text{and } \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_i - \ell_1, v; t) < \epsilon, \text{ for all } n \geq n_1. \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, there exists $n_2 \in \mathbb{N}$ so that

$$\frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q u_i - \ell_2, v; t) > 1 - \epsilon, \quad \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_i - \ell_2, v; t) < \epsilon$$

$$\text{and } \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_i - \ell_2, v; t) < \epsilon, \forall n \geq n_2.$$

Assume $n_0 = \max\{n_1, n_2\}$, thereafter for every $n_0 \leq n$, there exists, a natural number k so that

$$\alpha(Z^q u_k - \ell_1, v; t) > \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q u_i - \ell_1, v; t) > 1 - \zeta$$

and

$$\alpha(Z^q u_k - \ell_2, v; t) > \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q u_i - \ell_2, t) > 1 - \zeta.$$

Hence, we get

$$\alpha(\ell_1 - \ell_2, v; t) \geq \alpha(Z^q u_k - \ell_1, t) * \alpha(Z^q u_k - \ell_2, v; t)$$

$$> (1 - \zeta) * (1 - \zeta) > 1 - \epsilon.$$

As $0 < \epsilon$ is arbitrary, one conclude that $\alpha(\ell_1 - \ell_2, v; t) = 1, \forall t > 0$.

Similarly, it follows that $\beta(\ell_1 - \ell_2, v; t) = 0, \gamma(\ell_1 - \ell_2, v; t) = 0, \forall t > 0$.

Therefore, one deduce that $\ell_1 = \ell_2$. \square

Theorem 3.6. *Let $(\mathcal{V}, \alpha, \beta, \gamma, *, o)$ be a $N2NS$, and let $u = (u_i)$ be a sequence in \mathcal{V} such that μ -Zweier convergence of $Z^q u_i$ to ℓ holds. Then, the sequence $u = (u_i)$ also μ -Zweier ideal convergence to ℓ , i.e., \mathcal{J}_μ -convergence.*

Proof. Let $\mu - \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} Z^q u_i = \ell$. Given any $0 < t$ and $0 < \epsilon$, there exists $N_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ so that

$$\frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; t) > 1 - \epsilon, \quad \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; t) < \epsilon$$

and $\frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; t) < \epsilon$ for each $n \geq N_0$. Then the set

$$Q(\epsilon, t) = \left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; t) \leq 1 - \epsilon \text{ or } \right.$$

$$\left. \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; t) \geq \epsilon, \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; t) \geq \epsilon \right\}$$

$Q(\epsilon, t) \subseteq \{1, 2, 3, \dots, N_0 - 1\}$. Consequently, the set $Q(\epsilon, t)$ contains at most finitely many elements. Given that the ideal \mathcal{J} is admissible, it follows that $Q(\epsilon, t) \in \mathcal{J}$.

Therefore, we conclude that $\mathcal{J}_\mu - \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} Z^q u_i = \ell$. \square

Theorem 3.7. Let $(\mathcal{V}, \alpha, \beta, \gamma, *, o)$ be a N2NS, and let a sequenc $u = (u_i)$ in \mathcal{V} is μ - Zweier convergent to ℓ , the there exists a subsequence (u_{i_k}) of u is also convergent to same limit ℓ .

Proof. Let $\mu - \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} Z^q u_i = \ell$. Hence, for any $t > 0$ and $0 < \epsilon$, there exists a $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ so that

$$\frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; t) > 1 - \epsilon, \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; t) < \epsilon \text{ and}$$

$$\frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; t) < \epsilon \text{ for every } n_0 \leq n.$$

It is evident that for every $n_0 \leq n$, one can select $i_k \in J_n$ such that

$$\alpha(Z^q u_{i_k} - \ell, v; t) > \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; t) > 1 - \epsilon$$

,

$$\beta(Z^q u_{i_k} - \ell, v; t) < \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; t) < \epsilon$$

and

$$\gamma(Z^q u_{i_k} - \ell, v; t) < \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; t) < \epsilon.$$

Hence, $\mu - \lim Z^q u_{i_k} = \ell$. \square

Definition 3.8. Let $(\mathcal{V}, \alpha, \beta, \gamma, *, o)$ be a N2NS. A sequence $u = (u_i)$ in \mathcal{V} is known as μ - Zweier Cauchy, if for any $0 < t, \epsilon$, there exists $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ so that

$$\frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i, j \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q u_i - Z^q u_j, v; t) > 1 - \epsilon, \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i, j \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_i - Z^q u_j, v; t) < \epsilon$$

and $\frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i, j \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_i - Z^q u_j, v; t) < \epsilon, \forall i, j \geq n_0.$

Definition 3.9. Let $(\mathcal{V}, \alpha, \beta, \gamma, *, o)$ be a N2NS. A sequence $u = (u_i)$ in \mathcal{V} is known as a μ - Zweier ideal Cauchy, if for each $0 < \epsilon, t$, there exists a $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ in order that

$$\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i, k \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q u_i - Z^q u_k, v; t) > 1 - \epsilon \right\} \in \mathcal{F}(\mathcal{J}),$$

$$\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i, k \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_i - Z^q u_k, v; t) < \epsilon, \right\} \in \mathcal{F}(\mathcal{J}) \text{ and}$$

$$\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i, k \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_i - Z^q u_k, v; t) < \epsilon, \right\} \in \mathcal{F}(\mathcal{J})$$

Theorem 3.10. Let $(\mathcal{V}, \alpha, \beta, \gamma, *, o)$ be a N2NS. A sequence $u = (u_i)$ in \mathcal{V} is μ - Zweier ideal Cauchy sequence iff it is μ - Zweier ideal convergent.

Proof. Assume the sequence $u = (u_i)$ is μ - Zweier ideal Cauchy sequence but not convergent. Then, there exist, $k \in \mathbb{N}$ so that if one select

$$R(\epsilon, t) = \left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i, j \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q u_i - Z^q u_j, v; t) \leq 1 - \epsilon \text{ or} \right.$$

$$\frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i,j \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_i - Z^q u_j, v; t) \geq \epsilon, \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i,j \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_i - Z^q u_j, v; t) \geq \epsilon \}$$

and

$$S(\epsilon, t) = \left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; \frac{t}{2}) \leq 1 - \epsilon \text{ or } \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; \frac{t}{2}) \geq \epsilon \text{ and } \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; \frac{t}{2}) \geq \epsilon \right\}.$$

Then $R(\epsilon, t) \in \mathcal{J}$ implies $R^C(\epsilon, t) \in \mathcal{F}(\mathcal{J})$. Since

$$\frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q u_i - Z^q u_k, v; t) \geq \frac{2}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; \frac{t}{2}) > 1 - \epsilon,$$

$$\frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_i - Z^q u_k, v; t) \leq \frac{2}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; \frac{t}{2}) < \epsilon$$

and

$$\frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_i - Z^q u_k, v; t) \leq \frac{2}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; \frac{t}{2}) < \epsilon.$$

If $\frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; \frac{t}{2}) > \frac{1-\epsilon}{2}, \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; \frac{t}{2}) < \frac{\epsilon}{2}$ and

$\frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; \frac{t}{2}) < \frac{\epsilon}{2}$ respectively. Then, one obtain

$$\delta \left(\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q u_i - Z^q u_k, v; t) > 1 - \epsilon, \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_i - Z^q u_k, v; t) < \epsilon \text{ and } \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_i - Z^q u_k, v; t) < \epsilon \right\} \right) = 0,$$

that is, $R(\epsilon, t) \in \mathcal{F}(\mathcal{J})$, which contadicts our assumption. Therefore, sequence $u = (u_i)$ is μ -Zweier ideal convergent.

Conversely, Assume $\mathcal{J}_\mu - \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} Z^q u_i = \ell$. Take $\zeta > 0$, in such a way that $1 - \epsilon < (1 - \zeta) * (1 - \zeta)$ and $\epsilon > \zeta \diamond \zeta$. For all $t > 0$, construe

$$T(\zeta, t) = \left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; \frac{t}{2}) \leq 1 - \zeta \text{ or } \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; \frac{t}{2}) \geq \zeta, \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; \frac{t}{2}) \geq \zeta \right\} \in \mathcal{J}.$$

This implies $T(\zeta, t)^C \in \mathcal{F}(\mathcal{J})$. Assume $k \in T^c(\zeta, t)$. Then, one obtain

$$\frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{k \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; \frac{t}{2}) > 1 - \zeta, \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{k \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; \frac{t}{2}) < \zeta$$

$$\text{and } \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{k \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_i - \ell, v; \frac{t}{2}) < \zeta.$$

For every $\epsilon > 0$, one take

$$H(\epsilon, t) = \left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i,k \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q u_i - Z^q u_k, t) \leq 1 - \epsilon \text{ or } \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i,k \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_i - Z^q u_k, t) \geq \epsilon, \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{i,k \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_i - Z^q u_k, t) \geq \epsilon \right\}.$$

To show $H(\epsilon, t) \subset T(\zeta, t)$, let us suppose $l \in H(\epsilon, t)$, we have

$$\frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{l,k \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q u_l - Z^q u_k, v; \frac{t}{2}) \leq 1 - \epsilon, \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{l,k \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_l - Z^q u_k, v; \frac{t}{2}) \geq \epsilon$$

$$\text{and } \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{l,k \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_l - Z^q u_k, v; \frac{t}{2}) \geq \epsilon.$$

According to the above inequality, one characterize the next three illustration as:

Case 1: Let $\frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{l,k \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q u_l - Z^q u_k, v; t) \leq 1 - \epsilon$. Then

$$\frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{u \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q u_l - \ell, v; \frac{t}{2}) \leq 1 - \zeta, \text{ therefore } l \in T(\zeta, t).$$

Otherwise, if $\frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{l \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q x_{uv} - \ell, v; \frac{t}{2}) > 1 - \zeta$. Then, we have

$$1 - \epsilon \geq \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{l,k \in J_n} \alpha(Z^q u_l - Z^q u_k, v; t)$$

$$\geq \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{l \in J_n} \alpha \left(Z^q u_l - \ell, v; \frac{t}{2} \right) * \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{k \in J_n} \alpha \left(Z^q u_k - \ell, v; \frac{t}{2} \right)$$

$$> (1 - \zeta) * (1 - \zeta)$$

$$> 1 - \epsilon$$

a contradiction. Therefore $H(\epsilon, t) \subset T(\zeta, t)$.

Case 2: Consider $\frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{l,k \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_l - Z^q u_k, v; t) \geq \epsilon$. We get $\frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{l \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_l - \ell, v; \frac{t}{2}) \geq \zeta$,

hence $l \in T(\zeta, t)$. Otherwise, if $\frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{l \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_l - \ell, v; \frac{t}{2}) < \zeta$. Then, we obtain

$$\epsilon \leq \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{l,k \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_l - Z^q u_k, v; t)$$

$$\leq \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{l \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_l - \ell, v; \frac{t}{2}) \diamond \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{k \in J_n} \beta(Z^q u_k - \ell, v; \frac{t}{2})$$

$$< \zeta \diamond \zeta < \epsilon,$$

a contradiction. Hence $H(\epsilon, t) \subset T(\zeta, t)$.

Case 3: Consider $\frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{l,k \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_l - Z^q u_k, v; t) \geq \epsilon$. We get $\frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{l \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_l - \ell, v; \frac{t}{2}) \geq \zeta$, hence $l \in T(\zeta, t)$. Otherwise, if $\frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{l \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_l - \ell, v; \frac{t}{2}) < \zeta$. Then, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon &\leq \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{l,k \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_l - Z^q u_k, v; t) \\ &\leq \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{l \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_l - \ell, v; \frac{t}{2}) \diamond \frac{1}{\mu_n} \sum_{k \in J_n} \gamma(Z^q u_k - \ell, v; \frac{t}{2}) \\ &< \zeta \diamond \zeta < \epsilon, \end{aligned}$$

a contradiction. Hence $H(\epsilon, t) \subset T(\zeta, t)$.

Consequently, we deduce that $H(\epsilon, t) \subset T(\zeta, t)$, implying $H(\epsilon, t) \in \mathcal{J}$. Therefore, the sequence $u = (u_i)$ is a μ -Zweier ideal Cauchy. \square

We present the subsequent theorems without proof, as their proofs are straightforward:

Theorem 3.11. *Let $(\mathcal{V}, \alpha, \beta, \gamma, *, o)$ be a N2NS, and let $u = (u_i)$ be a sequence in \mathcal{V} . If u is a μ -Zweier Cauchy sequence, then u is also a μ -Zweier ideal Cauchy sequence.*

Theorem 3.12. *Let $(\mathcal{V}, \alpha, \beta, \gamma, *, o)$ be a N2NS, and let $u = (u_i)$ be a sequence in \mathcal{V} . If u is a μ -Zweier Cauchy sequence, then there exists a subsequence u_{i_j} of u that is an ordinary Zweier Cauchy.*

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